

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Sulfonylurea antidiabetics are associated with lower out-of-hospital cardiac arrest: Real-world data from population-based study

Talip E. Eroglu^{1,2,3} | Lixia Jia¹ | Marieke T. Blom¹ | Arie O. Verkerk¹
 Harsha D. Devalla^{1,4} | Gerard J.J. Boink^{1,4} | Patrick C. Souverein² |
 Antonius de Boer²

¹Department of Cardiology, Heart Center, Amsterdam UMC, University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam, The Netherlands

²Division of Pharmacoepidemiology and Clinical Pharmacology, Utrecht Institute for Pharmaceutical Sciences, Utrecht University, Utrecht, The Netherlands

³Department of Cardiology, Copenhagen University Hospital Herlev and Gentofte, Hellerup, Denmark

⁴Department of Medical Biology, Amsterdam UMC, University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam, The Netherlands

⁵Netherlands Heart Institute, Utrecht, The Netherlands

Correspondence

Hanno L. Tan, MD, PhD, Heart Center, Department of Cardiology Amsterdam UMC, University of Amsterdam, Meibergdreef 9, 1105 AZ, Amsterdam, The Netherlands.
 Email: h.l.tan@amc.uva.nl

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Aims: Out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA) mostly results from ventricular fibrillation (VT/VF), often triggered by acute myocardial infarction (AMI). Sulfonylurea (SU) antidiabetics can block myocardial channels (K_{ATP} channels), activated during AMI, thereby modifying action potential duration (APD). We studied whether SU drugs impact on cardiac conduction and whether these effects are related to APD changes.

Methods: We conducted a population-based case-control study of documented OHCA cases with diabetes and 697 non-OHCA cases. We studied the association of SU drugs (alone or in combination) with OHCA risk compared to metformin monotherapy, and compared to glimepiride, using multivariable logistic regression. We studied the effects of these drugs on APD during simulated ischaemia in human induced pluripotent stem cell-derived cardiac myocytes.

Results: Compared to metformin, use of SU drugs alone or in combination with metformin was associated with reduced OHCA risk ($OR_{SU\text{ drugs}}$ 0.6 [95% CI 0.4–0.9]). We found no association between SU drug users who suffered OHCA inside or outside of AMI. Reduction of OHCA risk compared to glimepiride was observed for glibenclamide (OR_{adj} 0.5 [95% CI 0.3–0.9]), but not glibenclamide (OR_{adj} 1.0 [95% CI 0.3–3.0]), tolbutamide, the association with reduced OHCA risk just fell below significance (OR_{adj} 0.6 [95% CI 0.3–1.002]). Glibenclamide was associated with ischaemia-induced APD shortening, while the other SU drugs were not. **Conclusions:** SU drugs were associated with reduced OHCA risk compared to metformin monotherapy, with glibenclamide having a lower risk.

KEYWORDS

ESCAPE-NET, K_{ATP} channels, sulfonylurea, sudden cardiac arrest

1 | INTRODUCTION

Out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA) is a leading cause of death in industrialized societies. OHCA is predominantly caused by ventricular tachycardia/ventricular fibrillation (VT/VF) that arises from disruptions in cardiac electrophysiology.¹ Diabetes mellitus is an important risk factor for OHCA.² Multiple pathophysiological changes in diabetes may result in VT/VF, in particular, development of ischaemic heart disease.² Myocardial ischaemia may lead to VT/VF by inducing various electrophysiological changes. One key mechanism is change in the duration of the action potential (AP) of ventricular cardiomyocytes. AP-shortening, following in large part from opening of myocardial **ATP-regulated K^+ channels** (K_{ATP} channels) during ischaemia and acute myocardial infarction (AMI),³ may facilitate re-entrant excitation and VT/VF.³ Conversely, AP-shortening during ischaemia and AMI may be a cardioprotective mechanism, and lack thereof may result in intracellular Ca^{2+} overload and delayed afterdepolarizations³ and/or impaired cell-to-cell transmission of the electrical wavefront;⁴ these changes may also culminate in VT/VF. Sulfonylurea (SU) drugs, used commonly to achieve glycaemic control in diabetes, exert their therapeutic action by blocking pancreatic K_{ATP} channels, thereby inducing release of insulin.⁵ Importantly, SU drugs may also block myocardial K_{ATP} channels,⁵ thereby potentially impacting on AP duration of ventricular cardiomyocytes. We therefore hypothesized that SU drugs impact on the risk of OHCA, especially during AMI. To test our hypothesis, we studied whether the use of SU drugs (alone or in combination with metformin) is associated with reduced OHCA risk compared with metformin (both designed for the treatment of type 2 diabetes), in a population-based case-control study based on data from an emergency medical services (EMS) attended OHCA registry, and stratified our analysis according to the immediate cause of OHCA (presence or absence of AMI), expecting that use of SU drugs is more strongly associated with lower OHCA risk in subgroups of OHCA cases who suffered OHCA in the presence of AMI than in the absence of AMI. Moreover, we studied the association between individual SU drugs (glibenclamide, gliclazide, tolbutamide) compared to glimepiride. In addition, we explored the underlying cellular electrophysiological mechanisms by performing patch-clamp studies in human-induced pluripotent stem cell-derived cardiomyocytes (hiPSC-CMs).

What is already known about t

- An increase in the incidence of cardiac arrest (OHCA) among individuals with diabetes mellitus (DM) represents a global public health concern.
- There is strong interest in minimizing OHCA risk in individuals with DM.
- A few experimental and observational studies suggest that some sulfonylurea drugs may reduce OHCA risk, but the evidence is inconclusive because these studies have other important limitations in the design.

What this study adds

- The effects of SU drugs on OHCA risk were studied in a large cohort specifically designed for this purpose (219 patients with ECG-documented OHCA).
- Use of SU drugs (alone or in combination with metformin) is associated with reduced OHCA risk compared with metformin monotherapy.
- Gliclazide, but not glibenclamide, decreased risk of OHCA compared with metformin. Tolbutamide is also associated with reduced OHCA risk, but this association just failed to reach statistical significance.

Studies (ARREST,⁶) registry in the study excluded cases without complete drug-use data at index date (OHCA date), those who suffered OHCA from non-cardiac causes (e.g., trauma, drowning), and those who had their second OHCA episode. Each case was matched to non-OHCA controls who were alive on the date of the OHCA using risk set matching based on age, sex, and comorbidities. In the original case-control data set, we included metformin in monotherapy or any SU drug in combination with metformin at index date, and excluded all persons

2.2 | Data sources

Details of the ARREST registry were reported previously.⁶ In short, ARREST is an ongoing population-based registry of all EMS-attended OHCA in one contiguous study region of the Netherlands, representative for the community at large (~2.6 million inhabitants, urban and rural areas, capture rate >90%). The ARREST study centre is notified by all dispatch centres in the study region of every EMS-attended OHCA. ECGs are collected from the manual defibrillator used by EMS personnel and/or the automated external defibrillator used by first responders or citizen-responders. Information from these ECGs with additional information from the dispatch centres and EMS personnel are used to verify the presence of VT/VF. The immediate cause of VT/VF was retrieved from hospital records and was classified as AMI, no AMI (any other cardiac cause) or unknown, as diagnosed by the treating cardiologist.⁶ These data were obtained for those individuals who survived to hospital admission. Drug-dispensing records in the year before OHCA was retrieved from the patients' pharmacist using standardized protocols. Controls were derived from the PHARMO Database Network, which contains drug-dispensing records from community pharmacies.⁷ We also obtained complete drug-dispensing records in the year before index date from controls. As virtually all individuals in the Netherlands are registered at a single pharmacy, drug-dispensing records are considered complete.

2.3 | Exposure of interest

We studied use of the most commonly prescribed SU drugs in the Netherlands (glibenclamide, glimepiride, gliclazide, tolbutamide) by using the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical classification (ATC) system (see Table S1 in the Supporting Information for the ATC codes). Use of metformin and SU drugs was defined as having a drug-dispensing record within 90 days before the index date, since, in the Netherlands, the average repeat prescription length for drugs used for chronic diseases is 90 days. We classified users of antidiabetics into one of the following mutually exclusive categories: (1) use of metformin alone and (2) use of SU drugs (alone or in combination with metformin).

2.4 | Covariates

As covariates, we assessed the following known risk factors for OHCA: cardiovascular disease, use of non-antiarrhythmic QT-

class 1 or 3 and/or non-cardiac QT-prol having a drug-dispensing record within We used a period of 90 days before indi antiarrhythmic drugs class 1 or 3 and/c drugs in order to adjust for the direct effects of these drugs. The cardiovascular in the analysis as proxies for cardiovascular of their direct effects on cardiac elect exposure window was set at 6 months.

2.5 | Cellular electrophysiology

The effects of the SU drugs on AP- ischaemia (SI) were measured in hiP human cell model for cardiac disease ; APs of hiPSC-CMs were recorded at c rated patch-clamp technique. APs wer duration at 90% of repolarization (dynamic clamp technique with injection fier K⁺ current (I_{K1}) was used to achi resting membrane potential. The effi shortening were studied during SI, indu lular glucose in combination with metab 2 mmol/L sodium cyanide (NaCn) and extended methods section is provided tion. The SU drug concentrations stu glimepiride 10 nM, gliclazide 10 μM, tol because they are reported to cause (I_{K,ATP}) in cardiac and skeletal muscle.^{9–1}

2.6 | Statistical analyses

We used multivariable logistic regressi strength of the association between SU d lating the odds ratio (OR) and 95% confi two models. By subselecting all individ metformin or SU drugs 90 days before th case-control data set, the original matc adjusted for age and sex (Model 1). adjusted for all covariates listed in Tabl conducted for the overall use of SU drugs and separately for use of SU drugs alone c min (reference: metformin alone). Subgrc

TABLE 1 Baseline characteristics of cases and controls

	Cases (n = 219)	Controls (n = 697)
Mean age, years (SD)	71.4 (10.3)	71.9 (10.0)
Male sex	168 (76.7)	556 (79.8)
Concomitant drug use		
Beta blockers	110 (50.2)	261 (37.4)
Calcium channel blockers	46 (21.0)	155 (22.2)
Antithrombotics	95 (43.4)	296 (42.5)
Diuretics	131 (59.8)	308 (44.2)
Renin-angiotensin system inhibitors	148 (67.6)	422 (60.5)
Nitrates	54 (24.7)	78 (11.2)
Statins	129 (58.9)	450 (64.6)
Vaughan-Williams class 1 or 3 antiarrhythmic drugs	14 (6.4)	10 (1.4)
Non-cardiac QT-prolonging drugs	13 (5.9)	33 (4.7)

Numbers are number (%) unless indicated otherwise. *P*-values are calculated using the Student's *t*-test or χ^2 statistics.

Use of beta blockers, calcium channel blockers, antithrombotics, diuretics, renin-angiotensin system inhibitors, nitrates and/or within 6 months before the index date. Use of Vaughan-Williams class 1 or 3 antiarrhythmic drugs and/or non-cardiac QT-prolonging drugs use within 90 days before the index date.

SU drugs only; (stage 2) metformin and SU drugs. Finally, we examined whether patient characteristics or concomitant drug use was different between users of individual SU drugs.

Comparisons for continuous variables were made with Student's *t*-test or analysis of variance (ANOVA). The χ^2 analyses were used when discrete variables were compared across groups. Statistical tests were two-tailed, with *P*-value of <.05 considered as statistically significant.

For the cellular electrophysiological studies, statistical analysis was carried out with SigmaStat 3.5 software and data are presented as mean $\pm$ SEM. Normality and equal variance assumptions were tested with the Kolmogorov–Smirnov and the Levene median test, respectively. Groups were compared using ANOVA based on ranks test (Kruskal-Wallis test) followed by Dunn's test. *P* < .05 was defined as statistical significance.

2.7 | Nomenclature of targets and ligands

Key protein targets and ligands in this article are hyperlinked to corresponding entries in <http://www.guidetopharmacology.org>, the common portal for data from the IUPHAR/BPS Guide to PHARMACOLOGY, and are permanently archived in the Concise Guide to PHARMACOLOGY 2019/20.¹³

male, Table 1, Figure 1). Among 10 5 complete medication records, 697 used SU drugs alone or SU drugs in combination with metformin (mean age 71.9 years, 79.5% male, Figure 1).

3.2 | Association between SU drugs and OHCA risk

Compared to use of metformin alone (cases: 49.8% of total cases), the overall use of SU drugs (cases: 49.8% of total cases) was associated with reduced risk of OHCA (OR_{SUdrugs} 0.6 [95% CI 0.5–0.9]). Use of SU drugs alone (cases: 30.1% of total cases) was associated with reduced OHCA risk (OR_{SUdrugs} 0.6 [95% CI 0.4–0.9]). Use of SU drugs in combination with metformin (cases: 30.1% of total cases) was associated with reduced OHCA risk (OR_{SUdrugs + metformin} 0.6 [95% CI 0.4–0.9]). The prevalence of statin use among metformin users was 58.9%. There is no evidence that users of SU drugs had a higher risk of AMI (OR_{AMI-SUdrugs} 0.6 [95% CI 0.4–1.1]; *P* = 0.7–1.2, Table 4). Next, we examined CVD risk factors compared to glimepiride, and

FIGURE 1 Flow chart of inclusion of out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA) cases OHCA, out-of-hospital cardiac arrest; VT/VF, ventricular tachycardia/ventricular fibrillation

TABLE 2 Use of sulfonylurea and the risk for out-of-hospital cardiac arrest compared to use of metformin in monotherapy

	Cases (n = 219)	Controls (n = 697)	Crud (mod)
Metformin alone	110 (50.2)	275 (39.5)	1.0 (r
Sulfonylurea drugs	109 (49.8)	422 (60.5)	0.7 ((
Sulfonylurea drugs alone	43 (19.6)	172 (24.7)	0.6 ((
Sulfonylurea drugs + metformin	66 (30.1)	250 (35.9)	0.7 ((

Use of metformin and/or sulfonylurea drugs was defined as use within 90
 Model 1: OR adjusted for age and sex.
 Model 2: OR adjusted for age, sex, use of cardiovascular drug use, Vaughai

TABLE 3 Characteristics of users of metformin alone, sulfonylurea drugs alone or sulfonylurea drugs + metformin

	Metformin alone	Sulfonylurea drugs alone	Sulfonylurea drugs + metformin
N	385	215	316
Age (years, standard deviation)	69.6 (10.1)	75.2 (9.7)	72.1 (9.5)
Sex male	302 (78.4)	162 (75.3)	260 (82.3)
Concomitant drug use			
Beta blockers	150 (39.0)	88 (40.9)	133 (42.1)
Calcium channel blockers	80 (20.8)	53 (24.7)	68 (21.5)
Antithrombotics	165 (42.9)	87 (40.5)	139 (44.0)
Diuretics	185 (48.1)	101 (47.0)	153 (48.4)
Renin-angiotensin system inhibitors	234 (60.8)	128 (59.5)	208 (65.8)
Nitrates	52 (13.5)	37 (17.2)	43 (13.6)
Statins	260 (67.5)	122 (56.7)	197 (62.3)
Vaughan-Williams class 1 or 3 antiarrhythmic drugs	8 (2.1)	7 (3.3)	9 (2.8)
Non-cardiac QT-prolonging drugs	24 (6.2)	10 (4.7)	12 (3.8)

Numbers are number (%) unless indicated otherwise. *P*-values are calculated using ANOVA or χ^2 statistics.

Use of metformin and/or sulfonylurea drugs was defined as use within 90 days before the index date. Use of beta blockers, antithrombotics, diuretics, renin-angiotensin system inhibitors, nitrates and/or statins was defined as use within 6 months before the index date. Use of Vaughan-Williams class 1 or 3 antiarrhythmic drugs and/or non-cardiac QT-prolonging drugs was defined as use within 90 days before the index date.

	Cases	Controls	Crude OR (model 1)	Adjusted OR (model 2)
OHCA-AMI	63	697		
Metformin alone	32 (50.8)	275 (39.5)	1.0 (reference)	1.0 (reference)
Sulfonylurea drugs	31 (49.2)	422 (60.5)	0.6 (0.4–1.1)	0.6 (0.4–1.1)
Sulfonylurea drugs alone	12 (19.0)	172 (24.7)	0.6 (0.30–1.2)	0.6 (0.3–1.2)
Sulfonylurea drugs + metformin	19 (30.2)	250 (35.9)	0.6 (0.36–1.2)	0.7 (0.4–1.2)
OHCA-no AMI	56	697		
Metformin alone	26 (46.4)	275 (39.5)	1.0 (reference)	1.0 (reference)
Sulfonylurea drugs	30 (53.6)	422 (60.5)	0.7 (0.4–1.3)	0.7 (0.4–1.2)
Sulfonylurea drugs alone	11 (19.6)	172 (24.7)	0.6 (0.3–1.3)	0.6 (0.3–1.3)
Sulfonylurea drugs + metformin	19 (33.9)	250 (35.9)	0.8 (0.4–1.5)	0.7 (0.4–1.4)

TABLE 4 Characteristics of in-hospital and out-of-hospital (OHCA) risk factors in the context of acute myocardial infarction (AMI)

The immediate cause of OHCA could only be obtained for those individuals who survived to hospital admission. Use of metformin and/or sulfonylurea drugs was defined as use within 90 days before the index-date.

Model 1: OR adjusted for age and sex.

Model 2: OR adjusted for age, sex, use of cardiovascular drugs, Vaughan-Williams class 1 or 3 antiarrhythmic drugs and non-cardiac QT-prolonging drugs.

Similar effects were found in a different set of experiments where we used 10 μ M of all drugs (Supplemental Figure S1).

prevalence of statin use was higher among controls. There was no further evidence that differences in

TABLE 5 Use of individual sulfonylurea drugs and risk of out-of-hospital cardiac arrest compared to use of glimepiride

	Cases (n = 219)	Controls (n = 697)	Crude OR (model 1)	Adjusted (model 2)
Glimepiride	58 (26.5)	164 (23.5)	1.0 (reference)	1.0 (reference)
Glibenclamide	12 (5.5)	29 (4.2)	1.2 (0.6–2.5)	1.3 (0.6–2.5)
Gliclazide	16 (7.3)	101 (14.5)	0.5 (0.3–0.8)	0.5 (0.3–0.8)
Tolbutamide	23 (10.5)	125 (17.9)	0.5 (0.3–0.9)	0.6 (0.3–0.9)

Not included in the table: Three controls that used multiple sulfonylurea drugs. Use of individual sulfonylurea drugs was defined as use within 90 days before the index-date.

Model 1: OR adjusted for age and sex.

Model 2: OR adjusted for age, sex, use of cardiovascular drugs, Vaughan-V antiarrhythmic drugs and non-cardiac QT-prolonging drugs.

Model 3: OR adjusted for age, sex, use of cardiovascular drugs, Vaughan-V antiarrhythmic drugs, non-cardiac QT-prolonging drugs and diabetes severity.

TABLE 6 Characteristics of individual sulfonylurea drug users

	Glimepiride	Glibenclamide	Gliclazide
N	222	41	117
Age, years, mean (SD)	72.0 (9.6)	73.6 (9.5)	73.8 (9.5)
Male, n (%)	167 (75.2)	33 (80.5)	97 (82.9)
Concomitant drug use, n (%)			
Beta blockers	95 (42.8)	14 (34.1)	53 (45.3)
Calcium channel blockers	50 (22.5)	11 (26.8)	32 (27.4)
Antithrombotics	89 (40.1)	21 (51.2)	54 (46.2)
Diuretics	114 (51.4)	21 (51.2)	57 (48.7)
Renin-angiotensin system inhibitors	144 (64.9)	25 (61.0)	80 (68.4)
Nitrates	34 (15.3)	5 (12.2)	16 (13.7)
Statins	140 (63.1)	17 (41.5)	72 (61.5)
Vaughan-Williams class 1 or 3 antiarrhythmic drugs	10 (4.5)	1 (2.4)	2 (1.7)
Non-cardiac QT-prolonging drugs	10 (4.5)	1 (2.4)	4 (3.4)

Numbers are number (%) unless indicated otherwise. *P*-values are calculated using ANOVA or χ^2 statistics.

Use of individual sulfonylurea drugs was defined as use within 90 days before the index date. Use of beta blockers, calcium channel blockers, antithrombotics, diuretics, renin-angiotensin system inhibitors, nitrates and/or statins was defined as use within 6 months before the index date. Use of Vaughan-Williams class 1 or 3 antiarrhythmic drugs and/or non-cardiac QT-prolonging drugs was defined as use within 90 days before the index date.

different effects on APD₉₀ changes during simulated ischaemia in cellular electrophysiologic studies in hiPSC-CMs.

To find the explanation for the decreased risk of OHCA upon use of SU drugs, we first investigated whether our finding was explained by differences in patient profiles, in particular, presence of factors that increase OHCA risk (i.e., cardiovascular comorbidity). Although the prevalence of statin use was higher among users of metformin, we found no further evidence that users of SU drugs had fewer prescrip-

tion (third-line treatment strategy) to metformin (first-line treatment strategy), use of SU drugs was associated with a lower OHCA risk. Furthermore, patients using metformin (our reference category) might have more diabetes severity (possibly having more advanced stage of diabetes) compared to only users of SU drugs still had lower OHCA risk. This provides additional support for the notion that SU

FIGURE 2 Effects of sulfonylurea drugs on action potentials (APs) during simulated ischemia (SI). **A**, Typical AP d_t in response to SI in absence (top panels) or presence (bottom panels) of 10 nM glibenclamide. SI-induced APD shortening is attenuated in the presence of glibenclamide. **B**, Average SI-induced APD changes in time (left panel) and average APD shortening at 15 min in the presence of glibenclamide (10 nM), gliclazide (10 μ M), glimepiride (10 nM), and tolbutamide (10 μ M). * indicates $P < .05$

metformin and survived (immortal) was not counted (in the metformin group) in the calculation of the effect size.

We found no stronger OHCA risk reduction associated with SU drugs in OHCA patients with proven AMI than in OHCA patients without proven AMI. This does not rule out that the OHCA risk-reducing effects of SU drugs occur in the presence of myocardial ischaemia, because myocardial ischaemia may have been present, but may not have led to AMI, e.g., because of spontaneous reperfusion by thrombus resolution and/or relaxation of the culprit vessel.¹⁴ This is of particular relevance, since AMI status could only be established in OHCA victims who survived to hospital admission and received car-

diac catheterization. The findings that the risk reduction was not explained by differences in patient characteristics or by differences in concomitant drug use suggest that the effect was due to the SU drugs. In addition, we studied distinct potencies to inhibit K_{ATP} channel. The findings that glibenclamide prevented OHCA more than the other SU drugs studied, in these findings were not consistent with the hypothesis that the SU drugs were grouped into two groups based on risk (gliclazide, tolbutamide, although not tolbutamide) and drugs that did not (glibenclamide). Cellular electrophysiologic studies provid-

of hypoglycaemia. A recent study reported that hypoglycaemic adverse events occurred in 10.6% of linagliptin users, but in 37.7% of glimepiride users.¹⁹ Still, given the low cost and demonstrated ability to reduce microvascular complications, SU drugs remain important in the treatment of diabetes mellitus type 2.²⁰ SU drugs may differ with respect to hypoglycaemia risk with glibenclamide carrying the highest and gliclazide the lowest risk of hypoglycaemia among second-generation SU drugs, which may also influence OHCA risk, since hypoglycaemia has been associated with QT-prolongation.¹² This may have influenced our outcome, since we could not control for hypoglycaemia in our study. This may have masked a possible association between glibenclamide and reduced OHCA risk, while we expect that the association between gliclazide and OHCA may have been less affected.

A previous study showed an increased mortality and cardiovascular risk with most first- and second-generation SU drugs compared with metformin in patients with or without previous AMI.¹⁷ However, results were not statistically different from metformin in both patients with AMI and those without AMI for gliclazide,¹⁷ indicating that gliclazide has a more favourable cardiovascular risk profile over other SU drugs. These findings were supported by another retrospective cohort study, where an increased total and cardiovascular mortality associated with glibenclamide compared with gliclazide was found.¹⁸ Our finding that gliclazide was associated with lower OHCA risk adds to the accumulating evidence of a favourable cardiovascular risk profile for gliclazide over other SU drugs. Regardless of the underlying mechanisms of our epidemiologic findings, our results are of clinical importance given the sharp rise in the prevalence of diabetes, and the fact that diabetes is associated with increased OHCA risk.² Therefore, a potential relation between gliclazide and lower OHCA risk and the mechanisms involved warrants future replication studies in other settings.

Animal studies on the effect of K_{ATP} channel modulators on cardiac arrhythmias produced seemingly contradictory findings. Glibenclamide was associated with decreased incidence of sustained VT and VF during ischaemia-reperfusion,²¹ but another study found increased occurrence of VT.²² Conversely, use of K_{ATP} channel openers was associated with increased incidence of VT/VF during ischaemia-reperfusion in one study,²¹ but with decreased incidence of arrhythmias in another study.²³ Moreover, opposite effects in the propensity for VF of K_{ATP} channel openers were demonstrated in different species.²³ While these drugs inhibited VF in anesthetized dogs, they promoted VF in rat hearts. These discrepancies indicate that the effects of K_{ATP} channel modulators in relation to cardiac arrhythmias depend upon the experimental model.¹⁹ The effects of SU drugs on

self-reported data, and VF ascertain e.g., fewer diabetes patients received rh et al. found lower VF incidence in the fir individuals with diabetes who used g individuals with diabetes who used no however, was small (VF occurred in two used glibenclamide, and six individuals w glibenclamide), while VT/VF episodes oc during the 36 hour period (and may no activity), and it was not specified glibenclamide at the time of those e reported that premature ventricular com tricular tachycardias following presumed less often during glibenclamide use than study.²⁶ However, the study was small (and ascertainment of ischaemia was ur segment changes on Holter recordings v leads.²⁶ Leonard et al. investigated in a whether SU drugs are associated with and ventricular arrhythmia, and found i glibenclamide, but not glimepiride, com mide and gliclazide were not examined).¹ findings with that study, because glipi. Netherlands, while gliclazide is not mark in all European countries. Moreover, th tinct, with far larger proportions of v among study participants in that study study by Leonard et al. had important relied solely on emergency department o mitted patients who died before hos important inclusion bias, particularly sinc reduced pre-hospital survival rates afte tainment of VF was not certain because than actual ECG recordings. Our study re ARREST registry was specifically designe to participation of all EMS departments both patients who survived to hospital a pre-hospital. Moreover, all cases in the A umentation to ascertain the presence or

4.1 | Strengths and limitation

A major strength of the ARREST registry mentation of VT/VF. Given the highly

particularly relevant in the present study, since patients with diabetes have reduced pre-hospital survival rates after OHCA.²³ Finally, information about drug use in cases and controls was based on drug-dispensing records, which is already one step closer to ascertainment of use than analysis of drug prescription.

Our study has also some limitations, e.g., data regarding the comorbidities could not be included in this study. To deal with this, we used concomitant drug use as proxy. Although we have no direct evidence that this method captures the most important cardiovascular diseases sufficiently accurately, we derive assurance that it did from our previous study in which we found similar results when we used this method or direct information on comorbidities.²⁸ Moreover, possible misclassification arising from this was probably similarly distributed between cases and controls. Furthermore, possible confounding by indication might play a role in our study since diabetes itself is a known risk factor for OHCA.² An approach could be to match case and control subjects on duration of diabetes. Here, duration of anti-diabetic treatment might be considered as a proxy for diabetes duration. However, the fact that we only had information on medication use 1 year before index year prevented us from identifying disease duration in all patients. To minimize this potential bias, we selected only patients with diabetes, aiming to make the cases and controls comparable with respect to underlying condition and excluded patients using second-line antidiabetic drugs or insulin to create a study population with a similar disease severity. Moreover, we compared users of SU drugs to users of metformin only. Still, (unmeasured) residual confounders could not be ruled out since data on several important risk factors such as physical activity, body mass index, left ventricular ejection fraction and blood glucose regulation were not available. Similarly, we had no information about smoking and alcohol use, although we cannot rule out that these confounders were unequally distributed between cases and controls, thereby leading to different baseline risk of cardiovascular disease between both groups. Also, we had no information about renal function and were not able to adjust for it. Yet, the risk of OHCA increases as kidney function declines.²⁹ Socioeconomic position is another risk factor for which we could not adjust because of lack of data, but it is of possible relevance, as it is likely associated with OHCA incidence.³⁰ Finally, misclassification in the use of metformin and SU drugs may have occurred, as we defined drug use as presence of drug-dispensing records ≤ 90 days prior to index date. We considered an exposure window of 90 days, since, in the Netherlands, the average repeat prescription length for drugs used for chronic diseases is 90 days. Lengthening of this exposure window might lead to inclusion of drugs that were not used at index date, confounding the analysis of direct drug

possibly low statistical power. Thus, final analyses should be interpreted with caution.

5 | CONCLUSION

SU drugs (alone or in combination with reduced OHCA risk compared with Gliclazide was associated with lower effects were not solely explained by eff ischaemia.

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There are no competing interests to decl

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data underlying this article cannot be shared publicly due to ethical/privacy reasons.

ORCID

Patrick C. Souverein <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7452-0477>

Antonius de Boer <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9485-8037>

Hanno L. Tan <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7905-5818>

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

